

APPLICATION OF COLOUR BASED MACHINE VISION TECHNOLOGY FOR MONITORING FRYING OIL DEGRADATION

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Abstract

Changes in colour of frying oils serve as a direct visual indicator of the oil's quality degradation when heated during deep-fat frying operations. As a result of oxidation and polymerisation the oil undergoes many changes including colour. Conventional chemical tests are reliable but time consuming and hence not suited for real time monitoring of the frying oil. This study describes the development and validation of colour measurement and methods for the on-line monitoring of oil quality during frying. Experiment was carried out for soybean oil, groundnut oil, sunflower seed oil. Controlled illumination conditions were employed in the acquisition of the oil sample images and colour properties were extracted in CIE L, CIE a, CIE b and Yellowness Index (YI) colour formats. In this study, the changes in colour with repeated deep fat frying were correlated with the chemical parameters of the oil's quality. These parameters were FFAs, peroxide value and the total polar compounds. The findings indicate a marked decrease in the colour strength and light transmission with increasing oil degradation. Frying oil quality using non-destructive colour-based machine vision showed very strong correlations ($r \geq 0.95$, $p < 0.01$) between CIE b, YI and Chemical indicators like FFAs, TPCs Peroxide Value.

Keywords: Total polar compounds, Colour value, Frying, Peroxide Value, Oil

Introduction

Deep fat frying leads to appealing colour, texture and taste, and hence frying is commonly utilised in the food processing and food serving industries. Food residue and moisture, as well as the oil's contact with oxygen at high temperatures during frying, lead to its degradation. The degradation happens by oxidative, thermal and hydrolytic reactions (Min and Choe, 2009). During oxidation, undesirable compounds are produced through the interaction of the components of oil. These include fatty acids, oxidised glycerides, polymers and coloured substances.

One of the obvious signs that frying oil deterioration leads to change in its colour. Oil is darkened when it is fried due to a series of chemical changes occurs in its constituents (Stevenson *et al.*, 1984). The oil turns brown because of the formation of oxidation products. In addition, it is turned brown by the polymerised products and by the migration of pigments of food into the oil (Stevenson *et al.*, 1984). At present oil colour is assessed either by the personal eye judgement or by the readings of a tintometer.

Laboratory tests such as fatty acids content, peroxides value and total polar compounds, are considered to be standard tests for determining oil deterioration (Fritsch, 1981). At present, measurement of the total polar compounds (TPC) is the most commonly used method to evaluate the quality of oil because it determines overall chemical degradation taking place in the oil (Farhoosh *et al.* 2010). However, these methods are time-consuming and not suited for real-time monitoring systems. Currently, techniques like machine vision are both rapid and non-destructive are attracting attention.

In a controlled lighting environment, objective and quantitative assessments of changes in colour can be made through computerised visual systems which extract the features from digital images. This technique gives additional information by measuring the changes in light transmission caused by the accumulation of coloured and polar degradation products in the oil (Zribi *et al.*, 2016).

Materials and Methods

Materials Refined soybean oil, groundnut oil, and cottonseed oil were bought from the local market. All chemicals used in the analysis were of analytical grade.

Heating and Frying Experiments Heating experiments were conducted by maintaining oils at 175 ± 5 °C, with samples collected at regular intervals of 2 hr and total 10 samples with replications were collected. Frying experiments involved frying French fries in vegetable oils heated at 175 ± 5 °C for 6 h daily in 2 cycle of 3 h for 3 days. Prepared oil samples stored in an air tight condition till analysis.

Machine Vision System The colour machine vision system was built to demonstrate its feasibility. A digital camera was installed vertically

above the substance sample placed in a clear glass beaker. The image was captured inside a closed chamber in presence of light. The camera settings remained consistent.

Mean colour values were extracted in RGB (Red, Green, Blue) and HSV (Hue, Saturation, Value) colour spaces using image processing software. Changes in colour parameters were used to measure oil darkening during heating and frying (Du & Sun, 2004).

Chemical Analysis

FFA, PV, and TPC were determined according to AOCS official methods (AOCS, 2017). All These Parameters was used to check efficacy of the developed system. All chemical analyses were done in replication.

Statistical Analysis Pearson correlation coefficient was used to check relationship between colour value and chemical quality indicator of frying oil. Statistical significance at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$ was checked.

Results and Discussion

Colour of oil subjected to heating and frying process for fresh sample and sample after end of process was found changed is observed clearly by naked eyes. This colour change was quantified using machine vision system. These images were captured from top of the sample and light source also located at the top of the sample so this colour value obtained by reflection of sample. CIE L, CIE a, CIE b and Yellowness Index are main four attributes which were used to quantify the colour of oil sample.

it was observed from the results that there was significant difference was found between fresh oil and 18 h fried oil sample. "CIE a" value of soybean oil, groundnut oil and cottonseed oil increased significantly after 18 h of frying. "CIE a" value of soybean oil, groundnut oil and cottonseed oil was found in the range of -14.83 to 1.31, -10.47 to -5.31 and -12.19 to 2.51 respectively. These results are shown in Fig. 2.

"CIE b" value (blue(-) to yellow(+)) for 0 to 18 h frying oil sample was analyzed in software and it was presented in Fig. 3. Results shows that initially it was increasing for soybean oil and cottonseed oil but after 10 h it shows no major changes and finally slight decrease at the end of frying. In groundnut oil it was increases with time but rate of increasing was decreases after 9 h of frying. "CIE b" values of soybean oil, groundnut oil and cottonseed oil samples ranged from 29.34 to 44.16, 9.44 to 47.46 and 29.94 to 44.20 respectively.

Yellowness index of frying oil sample was observed and results were plotted in Fig. 4. For fresh soybean oil, groundnut oil and cottonseed oil Yellowness index values were 52.61, 18.74 and 62.83 respectively. At the end of frying process yellowness index values were 107.65, 97.34 and 109.65 respectively. Fresh oil yellowness index was found increased significantly at the end of experiment of frying.

Fig. 1 Changes in "CIE L" value of different oil with respect

Fig. 2 Changes in "CIE a" value of different oil with respect

Fig. 3 Changes in "CIE b" value of different oil with respect

Fig. 4 Changes in yellowness Index of different oil with

heating time

Fig. 6 Changes in "CIE a" value of different oil with respect to

Fig. 4.29 Changes in "CIE b" value of different oil with respect to

Fig. 4.30 Changes in yellowness Index of different oil with respect to

Colour changes during heating

CIE L" value (Lightness Index) of oil with respect to heating time was measured. From Fig. 5 it was clearly observed that there was no particular trend observed for change of lightness in soybean oil, groundnut oil and cottonseed oil. Data analysis shows that there was no significant change in oil lightness with frying time. CIE L value of soybean oil, groundnut oil and cottonseed oil before heating was 42.77, 48.28 and 44.99 respectively. Maximum value of CIE L during heating was 47.70 (10 h), 48.45 (2 h) and 46.87 (10 h) for soybean oil, groundnut oil and cottonseed oil respectively.

"CIE a" value (green(-) to red(+)) of heating oil samples of different heating time was measured and it was observed from the results that there was no significant difference was found between maximum number of sample. Results were shown in Fig. 6 and line graph presents more or less parallel line to the X-axis. "CIE a" value of

soybean oil, groundnut oil and cottonseed oil was found in the range of -14.91 to -14.83, -15.19 to -10.47 and -12.19 to 11.64, respectively. "CIE b" value (blue(-) to yellow(+)) for 0 to 20 h heating oil sample was analyzed in software and it was presented in Fig. 7. Results show that, trend was found increasing for different type of oil. Exception was that for sample of 14 h heated groundnut oil and 10 and 20 h heated cottonseed oil. "CIE b" value decrease than previous sample. "CIE b" values of soybean oil, groundnut oil and cottonseed oil samples ranged from 31.63 to 47.00, 9.45 to 40.48 and 29.94 to 41.33 respectively. Yellowness index of heating oil sample was observed and results were plotted in Fig. 8. For fresh soybean oil, groundnut oil and cottonseed oil Yellowness index values were 60.66, 18.74 and 62.83 respectively. At the end of heating process yellowness index values were 85.49, 75.44 and 128.46 respectively. Exception was that for sample of 14 h heated groundnut oil and 10 h heated cottonseed oil yellowness index

decrease than previous sample. Fresh oil yellowness index was found increased significantly at the end of experiment of heating.

In all sample colour attribute was observed and it was noticed that lightness decreases when oil undergoes more frying. "CIE a" value shows increasing trend for frying and heating and has little but noticeable effect on "CIE a" value. "CIE b" value was observed increasing in both heating and frying case for oil with some unexpected changes. Yellowness index for oil shows increasing trend was observed for heating and frying.

Researchers reported that that colour value of sunflower oil significantly ($P < 0.05$) increases. Moreover, yellow value of oil change after every 2h of frying and it was 30.85 after 14 h of frying and red value of colour was not increasing significantly during 0 to 2 h and 4 to 8 h of frying (Manral *et al.*, 2008). Oil samples shows decrease in L values (lightness) and increase in a and b values of oil during frying. Furthermore, L value of fresh sunflower oil was 61.25 and it was decreased to 56.36 and a and b value of fresh sunflower oil -3.30 and 10.24 and it was increased to -2.20 and 20.49 respectively (Maskan, 2003). Earlier researchers also reported that oil colour intensity change from yellow to orange brown when it used for frying. (Tan *et al.*, 1985).

Darkening of oil and yellow colour development is due to carotenoids, xanthophylls, carbon particle formation due to carbonization, phenolic compound and non-enzymatic browning reaction (Paul *et al.*, 1997). Oil has light yellow colour when it was not used and changes to more yellow to orange brown when it was heated. These changes are combined results of oxidation, polymerization and other chemical changes (Tan *et al.*, 1985). Colour change after frying of any product is characterized by two pathways, either because of polymerization and its accumulation in oil during frying or because of transfer of colour pigments to frying oil during frying from product which is being fried (Choe and Min, 2009, Moreira, 2014).

The chemical properties shows very strong positive ($r > 0.85$) and significant correlation CIE b value, yellowness index of heated soyabean oil sample. CIE b value and yellowness index which was measured by image analysis system showed strong positive correlation ($r > 0.9$) with chemical properties ($p < 0.05$). In case of heated groundnut oil, CIE b value and yellowness index shows strong positive and significant correlation ($r > 0.9$, $p < 0.01$) with chemical properties of oil. CIE b value of heated cottonseed oil sample shows good positive and significant correlation ($r > 0.8$, $p < 0.01$) with TPC, FFA and PV of heated cottonseed oil. Yellowness index also shows positive and significant correlation ($r > 0.75$, $p < 0.01$).

Soybean oil used for frying also correlated with same chemical properties and it shows non-significant correlation between CIE b value and chemical properties except total polar compound ($p > 0.05$) whereas, yellowness index of oil shows strong positive correlation with TPC, FFA and PV ($r > 0.9$, $p < 0.01$). CIE b value and yellowness index of groundnut oil used for frying shows high positive correlation ($r > 0.9$, $p < 0.01$) with measured chemical properties. CIE b value and yellowness index by colour measuring system having r value more than 0.85. For cottonseed oil which was used for frying, yellowness index of cottonseed oil have high correlation ($r > 0.9$, $p < 0.01$) with TPC, FFA and PV of oil. CIE b value of color measuring system and image analysis system shows non-significant ($p > 0.05$) and significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation respectively.

Summary and conclusion

The results clearly indicate that, for all oil samples, total polar compounds, viscosity, and the yellowness index increase consistently with changes in the chemical quality of the oil, making them reliable

indicators of oil degradation. When heating and frying were compared, the CIE b value showed a weaker relationship with chemical properties during frying than during simple heating. Yellowness index shows opposite results than CIE b Value, which presents strong relationship with chemical indices under frying conditions and can be more effective indicator of quality degradation during cooking processes.

This research observations offer base for the future study and researchers can examine wide range of edible oils to confirm these results. This machine vision method can be developed for real time analysis with non-destructive tools for monitoring of quality changes in cooking conditions.

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